

A Comparative Study of English and Arabic Proverbs: Natural Semantic Metalanguage Approach

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Abstract: This study highlights the similarities and differences between two proverbs that are equivalent in meaning but originate from different cultures. Each proverb is traced to its culture and language, but still, they both share the same meaning. There are differences between them that could be explained by using natural semantic metalanguage. Using NSM, the hidden cultural messages could be brought to surface. The findings and results of this research proved that investigating both of Arabic and English proverbs culminated in results that showed that the differences between them could only be analyzed by NSM approach that showed the variation and difference in meaning. The findings of this study build a good base and provide scope for researchers in the future to work on the field of proverbs using NSM approach. It gives solutions for the lexical dilemma that is created because of culturally bound terms that generally can be analyzed only by paraphrasing.

Keywords: Adverbs, Contrastive, NSM, Substantives, Egyptian Arabic, English, Arabic.

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Introduction

Humans use the Language as tool for communication between one individual and another. In addition to that, there are expressive functions and social functions of the language (Lyon, 1977, 51). However, the diversity of language use due to expressive and social influences is still related to the same concept. In other words, a concept that exists in the human mind can be conveyed in different and varied ways. This link between concepts and language has long been stated by Saussure in his book *Course de Linguistic Generale* which is considered to be revolutionizing in that time. This study holds a contrastive study between two adverbs from English and Arabic language that have the equivalent meaning, but expressed in different words. Through this study, the researcher investigates those proverbs and analyzes them using natural semantic metalanguage approach to show the difference between them from the perspective of Natural Semantic Metalanguage.

The theory of Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM) is recognized as a relatively modern approach to semantic studies that is capable of producing an adequate analysis of meaning. This is because it depends mainly on the explication technique, the results of the analysis of meaning in a language have approached the postulate of semantic science which states that one form for one meaning and one meaning for one form. In other words, one lexicon item is able to convey one meaning or one meaning is expressed by one lexicon item. At the same time, it will prevent us from describing the meanings that go around and around just to deliver the meaning of one lexicon. (Sudipa, 2005:139).

NSM theory is designed to exclude all meanings, both lexical meaning, illocutionary meaning and grammatical meaning. Based on this theory developed by Anna Wierzbicka (1996) and her followers such as (Goddard,1996), this theory was created to solve the lexical dilemma created by culture-bound terms that have no equivalent lexically.

The theory of NSM (Natural Semantic Metalanguage) is designed to exclude all meanings, both lexical meaning, illocutionary meaning and grammatical meaning. This theory can be used to explain the expressions that are culturally bound. Proverbs represent one of the most prominent aspects of each culture. Proverbs are always an honest and lively realization of cultures. This paper will use NSM theory to analyze two adverbs from different cultures using natural semantic primes.

Supporters of this theory believe that the natural condition of a language is to maintain one form for one meaning and one meaning for one form. This principle is not only applied to grammatical construction, but also to words. In this theory, explication is framed in a metalanguage that comes from natural language. This explication can be understood by all native speakers of the language concerned (Wierzbicka, 1996:10, Mulyadi, 1998:34, and Sudipa, 2004).

One of the main assumptions of NSM theory is that meaning cannot be described without an underlying set of meanings. This assumption is based on the understanding that the meaning of a lexicon is a configuration of the original meaning, not determined by other meanings in the lexicon. The original meaning is a set of meanings that cannot be changed (Goddard, 1996: 2). This meaning reflects the basic human mind. The original meaning can be extracted from natural language which is the only way to represent meaning (Wierzbicka, 1996:31). The explication of the meaning must include the meaning of words that are intuitively related or at least have the same field of meaning, and the meanings of these words are analyzed based on their components. A set of original meanings is expected to be able to explain complex meanings into simpler ones without having to go around and round, as stated by (Wierzbicka, 1996:12, Goddard, 1996:2) in the following quote:

It is impossible to define all words. In defining we employ a definition to express the idea which we want to join to the defined words; and if we then wanted to define "the definition" still other words would be needed, and so on to infinity. Considering the quote above, especially the search for complex meanings in a simpler way is very possible. This is because in the original meaning there is regularity. If the entire lexicon is analyzed in depth, it is estimated that regular features can be found, and if the original meaning is found it will be easier to find even complex meanings. This process can be achieving by analyzing based on semantic primes; the main aspects defined by Anna Wierzbicka to be used as tool for analyzing bigger structures that pose lexical dilemma because they are culturally bound terms that cannot be expressed lexically and there is no equivalent expression to them. They could have some terms that are similar in meaning, but still there is difference in meaning. The message delivered lexically would not be accurate.

Proverbs are expressions that contain implied meanings that can be understood by listeners or readers because they live in the same cultural surroundings. Proverbs can be defined as groups of words or sentences that have a fixed arrangement, usually symbolizing a certain meaning. Second, proverbs are short, dense expressions or sentences, containing comparisons, advice, principles of life, and rules to behave based on them.

Proverbs can be used as a wise way to reprimand someone so that the person is not offended. Each culture has a treasure of proverbs that makes this culture very unique from other cultures. Proverbs are considered to be one of the explicit products of culture. The meaning of each proverb is dependent on its culture. The meaning cannot be delivered devoid of the context of its culture. This study focuses on investigating two proverbs that come from two opposing cultures; English culture and Arab culture; each of them delivers the message beyond the proverb based on its contextualized culture. Here, the revolutionary theory of Anna Wierzbicka is used to apply analysis on those two proverbs from the perspective of NSM theory.

NSM complies with the common base of all language as it is considered to be a language that is minimized and depends on the basic pillars or a group of semantic primes that were defined by the theorist who devised NSM. Their study resulted in those universal semantic primes that are about 63 that are classified based on their grammatical characteristic to help researchers find the meaning and interpretation for any utterance that is dependent on culture only to be interpreted.

Those semantic primes can be explained as follows:

Substantives	I, you, someone, people, something/thing, body
Relational substantives	Kind, part
Determiners	This, the same, other/else/another
Quantifiers	One, two, some, all, much/many, little/few
Evaluators	Good, bad
Descriptors	Big, small
Mental predicates	Think, know, want, feel, see, hear
Speech	Say, words, true
Actions, events, movement	Do, happen, move

Existence, possession	Be (somewhere), there is, be (someone/something), (is) mine
Life and death	Live, die
Time	When/time, now, before, after, a long time, a short time, for some time, moment
Space	Where/place, here, above, below, far, near, side, inside, touch (contact)
Logical concepts	Not, maybe, can, because, if
Intensifier, augments	Very, more
Similarity	like/as/way

Fig. 1: Universal Semantic Primes according to Levisen and Waters, 2017

According to Wierzbicka, the core of NSM depends mainly on the fact that those simple keys that are used to deliver the meaning of more complicated concepts should not be complicated. They should be understood by everybody. The interpretation made should not omit or elaborate on the meaning delivered. It should be delivered accurately.

There are a lot of studies that were done using natural semantic metalanguage approach. The first study entitled "MAKNA VERBA 'MEMBERSIHKAN' DALAM BAHASA NIAS: PENDEKATAN METABAHASA SEMANTIK ALAMI" was written by Kalvintinus Ndruru in August 2020. This research is focused on investigating the meaning of configuration and analyzing the explanation of the verb "clean" in Nias language through the orientation of Natural Semantic Metalanguage (MSA) theory. This investigation was conducted by applying a qualitative descriptive research approach.

The second study entitled "BASIC SOCIAL CATEGORIES: NATURAL SEMANTIC META- LANGUAGE (NSM) APPROACH" was written by Guli Ergasheva, Doctor of Philological sciences. This study revolves around the NSM analysis that was established by A. Wierzbicka, and its focus on developing the structure of the main social categories.

The third study entitled "Revisiting the Universality of Natural Semantic Metalanguage: A View through Finnish" was written by Ulla Vanhatalo, Heli Tissari & Anna Idström. The aim of this research is to draw attention to the basic aspects of the NSM theory with regard to universal aspects of NSM concepts that are based on language and those that are based on English language.

The fourth study entitled "KAJIAN METABAHASA SEMANTIK ALAMI VERBA MELIHAT DALAM BAHASA Bali" was written by the researcher Ni Wayan Suastini. This study uses the Natural Semantic Metalanguage (MSA) approach, which is a semantic theory that uses a set of default meanings, which was first developed by Weirzbicka. This study focused on the meaning of one Balinese verb, namely the verb (see) using NSM approach.

The fifth study entitled "VERBA LEMPAR BAHASA BALI: KAJIAN METABAHASA SEMANTIK ALAMI" was written by Putu Ariana and Komang Sulatra. This study investigated "throwing verbs" in Balinese language as they have a variation of lexical meanings. Those meaning are analyzed based on NSM approach.

The sixth study entitled "STRUKTUR SEMANTIS VERBA "MEMBAWA" BAHASA SUNDA: KAJIAN METABAHASA SEMANTIK ALAMI" was written by Wiya Suktiningsih. The purpose of this study is to define the real meaning of the verb "membawa" in the language of Sunda lexically.

The seventh study was entitled "Vocabulary of Colors in Sundanese Language (Natural Semantic Metalanguage Approach" and was written by the researcher Santy Yulianti. The writer in this study used the approach of NSM to describe colors in the language of Sunda which are equivalent to the ones in Indonesian language. That is to say the main aspect of focus in this study is colors and the vocabulary attached to colors, considering the fact that the nature of Sunda is affected by having many colors due to natural setting of Sunda.

The eighth study entitled "A Comparison of English and Japanese Proverbs Using Natural Semantic Metalanguage" was written by the researcher MILES NEALE. This study made a contrastive and comparative studies between two different verbs belonging to different cultures and languages, namely Japanese and English language. Both of the verbs are equivalent in meaning, but still each of them is culturally bound proverbs. This study's main aspect of focus is proverbs and it is different from previous studies as it tackles the analysis of proverbs using natural semantic metalanguage approach.

The ninth study entitled "A Comparative Study of English and Chinese Proverbs Using Natural Semantic Metalanguage Approach" was written by the researcher Qiling Wu. This study is made to highlight the similar and different aspects between two equivalent proverbs that share the same meaning, but they are originally from two different cultures of China and England. This focuses on investigating proverbs as cultural artifacts.

Research Methodology

This study investigates the difference between two verbs that are from different cultures, but have the same meaning though they are different lexically. The analysis done in this study depends mainly on natural semantic metalanguage to interpret and establish the explication for each of the two verbs. The analysis is based on the theory of Anna Wierzbicka of NSM which was established by her together with Goddard.

The analysis in this study is done by using semantic primes that defines the sophisticated terms and have them dissolving into simpler terms that cannot be simplified more than that by using NSM semantic primes which are considered to be the simplest base that could be reached to analyze and explicate the realization of meanings for both of the two verbs. The analysis done by using the simple semantic primes is known as "explications", which is considered to be sort of paraphrasing that tends to shorten the meaning that is given in its elaborated version. (Goddard 2002, 7). The use of these semantic primes that are done in their simplest form gives the actual interpretation of the terms that are culturally dependent ones; in this case the two proverbs used in this paper.

The model of analysis for proverbs in NSM is based on five main features established by Goddard (2009). Those five aspects upon which the analysis of proverbs is done based on NSM are "traditionality, recurrent situation, advice, analogy, and status as folk wisdom". Those aspects are defined to tackle the analysis of proverbs, as proverbs are used as the source of folk wisdom because they are part that is inseparable and rooted in every culture for a very long time and can be traced to old ancestors. The emphasis thus is on the other three factors of Goddard's model. The main component, [a] recurrent situation, portrays the circumstance that the proverbial proverb cautions us against. The second factor, [b] advice, portrays the ethical illustration of a precept. The last component, [c] similarity or analogy, portrays the wisdom involved in a precept and a big motivator for it as well.

The main object of this study is one English proverb and two proverbs that are often used by Egyptian culture and folks as a source of wisdom. The English proverb is "Attack is the best form of Defense". The two equivalent proverbs from Egyptian Arabic and culture are "Inn lamm takon ze'ban aka-lat-ka Az-ziaa'b" which means "If you are not a wolf, you will be eaten by wolves" and the other one is "Itghadda beeh 'abl ma ye'ashsha beek" which means "you should have him as your lunch before he has you as his supper". The original form of the English proverb is often used in the same exact meaning as "AL-Hugoom khairu wasilatan leldi-faa" which means "Attack is the best way for defense". That means that there are three forms of proverbs that are used in Egyptian Arabic and some of them are used in other Arabic dialects that have equivalent meaning with different contexts.

The popular proverb is intended to show that precautionary strike is simply the most ideal way to guard yourself against attacks. It was mainly used to consider military assaults however it is presently utilized broadly, in sports and in regular daily activities. The first time this proverb was used in the American war by American soldier to state that they should attack first so they can become safe and not exposed to threat of attacks.

Results and Discussions

ANALYSIS: 'Attack is the best Form of Defense'.

Proverb 1: Attack is the best Form of Defense.

The analysis will be done by introducing the context in which this proverb is used. This context is taken from "The free dictionary". According to the definition mentioned in this dictionary, Launching an offensive is the best way to protect oneself.

Example: I need to start some rumors about Dean, before he comes after me. I know it sounds harsh, but attack is the best form of defense! In this text, the message that needs to be delivered is that do not wait till you get attacked by someone, you start attacking them first. To be safe, you need to secure yourself by attacking first.

[a] Recurrent situation

Something like this often happens:

Someone does something because this someone does not want something to happen to himself before this something happens to himself, this someone does something first.

That someone thinks when that someone does that thing, bad things will not happen to this someone.

From the recurrent situation aspect, there is a model to follow that usually when people do not want to have something bad happening to themselves, they should start attacking people first or initiating the bad thing to others before it happens to themselves.

[b] Advice

when someone does something because this someone does not want something bad to happen it is good if this someone does it before someone else does it to himself.

The advice here is if someone is afraid of being attacked first, they should start attacking others first. Regardless of the controversial message delivered by this proverb, but it is widely used to deliver the advice of initiating something against people is better than waiting for people to hurt you first.

[c] Analogy

it is often like this:

someone does something because this someone does not want bad thing to happen to himself. This someone does that thing first. This someone does not want someone else does that thing to himself first.

If someone does not do that thing first, something bad will happen.

The analogy extracted from this proverb is that any action, saying or anything that you are worried will be happening to you, if you are worried that it will happen to you, you do it first. Whether sport, someone insults you, in study, work. Actually, it can be used in a wide range of situations.

Proverb 2: "Inn lamm takoon ze'ban akalatla Alzi'aab" / If you are not a wolf, you will be eaten by wolves.

The analysis will be done by introducing the context in which this proverb is used. This context is taken from "The encyclopedia of proverbs". According to it, if you did not devour people, people will devour you.

Example:

"You should avenge yourself, "Inn lamm takoon ze'ban akalatla Alzi'aab"/ If you are not a wolf, you will be eaten by wolves

[a] Recurrent situation

something like this often happens:

someone does something because this someone does not want something bad happen.

before this something happens to himself, this someone does something first.

That someone thinks when that someone does that thing, bad things will not happen.

From the recurrent situation aspect, there is a model to follow that usually when people do not want to have something bad happening to themselves, they should start attacking people first or initiating the bad thing to others before it happens to themselves. Wolves are wild animals and they devour on preys. The model here is that you start doing bad thing to people, before they do it to you.

[b] Advice

when someone does something because this someone does not want something bad to happen

it is good if this someone does it before someone else does it to himself.

The advice here is if someone is afraid of being devoured by wolves/ Attacking first, they should start attacking others first/ devouring on preys that would turn into wild animals if they were not devoured first.

[c] Analogy

it is often like this:

someone does something because this someone does not want bad thing to happen to himself. This someone does that thing first. This someone does not want someone else does that thing to himself first.

If someone does not do that thing first, something bad will happen.

The analogy extracted from this proverb is that if you did not hurt people first, they will hurt you. If you did not devour on preys (people), they will turn into wild animals (wolves) and will devour you first before you do it. It gives the reader justification to start doing bad thing with the pretense that if you did not start bad thing to others first, it will be your turn to be exposed to injustice.

Proverb 3: "Itghadda beeh 'abl ma ye'ashsha beek" / "you should have him as your lunch before he has you as his supper".

The analysis will be done by introducing the context in which this proverb is used. This context is taken from "The encyclopedia of proverbs". According to it, if you did not eat people as your main meal, people will have you as their next meal "

Example:

"You should Hurt your enemy, "Itghadda beeh 'abl ma ye'ashsha beek" / "you should have him as your lunch before he has you as his supper".

[a] Recurrent situation

Something like this often happens:

someone does something before someone because this someone does not want something bad happen.

before this something bad happens to himself, this someone does something first.

That someone thinks when that someone does that thing before someone else, bad thing will not happen to that someone.

From the recurrent situation aspect, there is a model to follow that usually when people do not want to have something bad happening to themselves, they should start hurting people first or conspiring against them first, so they do not give chance to others to hurt them. It means doing the bad thing to others before it happens to themselves. Wolves are wild animals and they devour on preys. The model here is that you start doing bad thing to people, before they do it to you. Meals are used here to express the order of events happening as there is breakfast, lunch, and supper. So, starting by one meal that comes before the other to guarantee that you have the imitation to start doing something to others, so you are safe.

[b] Advice

when someone does something before someone this someone does not want something bad to happen.

It is good if this someone does it before someone else does it.

The advice here is if someone is afraid of being hurt by someone/ they should conspire against them first. The metaphor expression used is "eating". It means, if you do not want to be eaten by others, eat them first. The advice is "Act attackingly before you get attacked"

[c] Analogy

it is often like this:

someone does something before someone. This someone does not want bad thing to happen to himself. This someone does that thing first. This someone does not want someone else does that thing to himself first.

If someone does not do that thing first, something bad will happen.

The analogy extracted from this proverb is that if you did not attack or hurt people first, they will end up hurting you. If you did not eat (people), they will eat you as their meal. The analogy here is "meals" and eating concepts

Attack is the best form of Defense	" Inn lamm takoon ze'ban akalatla Alzi' aab /" / If you are not a wolf, you will be eaten by wolves
[a] Recurrent situation something like this often happens: someone does something because this someone does not want something bad happen. before this something happens to himself, this someone does something first. That someone thinks when that someone does that thing, bad things will not happen.	[a] Recurrent situation something like this often happens: someone does something because this someone does not want something bad happen. before this something happens to himself, this someone does something first. That someone thinks when that someone does that thing, bad things will not happen.
[b] Advice when someone does something because this someone does not want something bad to happen it is good if this someone does it before someone else does	[b] Advice when someone does something because this someone does not want something bad to happen it is good if this someone does it before someone else does
[c] Analogy it is often like this: someone does something because this someone does not want bad thing to happen to himself. This someone does that thing first. This someone does not want someone else does that thing to himself first.	[c] Analogy it is often like this: someone does something because this someone does not want bad thing to happen to himself. This someone does that thing first. This someone does not want someone else does that thing to himself first.

Fig. 2: Explications of the first proverb and the second Proverb using semantic primes:

Attack is the best form of Defense	Itghadda beeh ‘abl ma ye’ashsha beek / “you should have him as your lunch before he has you as his supper”.
[a] Recurrent situation something like this often happens: someone does something because this someone does not want something bad happen. before this something happens to himself, this someone does something first. That someone thinks when that someone does that thing, bad thing will not happen.	[a] Recurrent situation Something like this often happens: Someone does something before someone because this someone does not want something bad happen. before this something bad happens to himself, this someone does something first. That someone thinks when that someone does that thing before someone else, bad thing will not happen to that
[b] Advice when someone does something because this someone does not want something bad to happen	[b] Advice when someone does something before someone this someone does not want something bad to happen.
[c] Analogy it is often like this: someone does something because this someone does not want bad thing to happen to himself. This someone does that thing first. This someone does not want someone else	[c] Analogy it is often like this: someone does something before someone. This someone does not want bad thing to happen to himself. This someone does that thing first. This someone does not want someone

Fig. 3: Explications of the first proverb and the third Proverb using semantic primes:

Conclusion

This study has shown that English and two Arabic proverbs that were introduced in this study share many similarities and slight variations when analyzed based on semantic primes. They are almost identical when analyzed using semantic primes, but still the recurrent situation was analyzed with slightly different variation in the third proverb. The proverbs are almost identical in meaning, but each has different context. When analyzed using NSM, they were proved to be almost the same meaning lexically. There were not many studies done on NSM using Arabic language and Arabic proverbs. Hoping this study will build a good base for researchers to accumulate on this study and start opening a wider scope of researches that are done on Arabic language using natural semantic language approach.

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